

mnemonic techniques in teaching a foreign language. Proceedings of SOCIOINT 2019- 6th International Conference on Education, Social Sciences and Humanities 2019 June 24-26; Istanbul, Turkey.

8. Scruggs, T. E., Mastropieri, M. A., McLoone, B. B., Levin, J. R., & Morrison, C. R. Mnemonic facil-

itation of learning disabled students' memory for expository prose. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 1987 Mar; 79(1): 27-34.

9. Shmidman, A., Ehri, L. Embedded picture mnemonics to learn letters. *Scientific Studies of Reading*. 2010; 14(2): 159-182

DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE-COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the problem of development of cognitive communicative competence of high school students in teaching foreign language. In this article the approaches of the formation of this competence in FLT by means of internet resources will be considered as the first step of training highly- qualified future specialists who will meet all the requirements of modern society, at the same time modernizing education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Keywords: cognitive - communicative competence, modernization, high school, foreign language teaching, Internet resources.

Nowadays in connection with modern tendencies in the development of education system of Kazakhstan, there is a need for specialists who are able to work and compete in international labour market, and who have intercultural communicative competencies, including cognitive- communicative competence. So, according to this education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan joined the Bologna process which gave us an opportunity to enter the European system of education.

The signing of the Bologna Agreement by Kazakhstan, under which a single European educational space is being created, was an inevitable consequence and an indispensable condition for the implementation of the transformations taking place in our country in general and in the system of foreign language education in particular. Changing socio-cultural conditions, the developing mobility and openness of society, the need for the convertibility of Kazakhstani diplomas make it necessary to take into account global trends in reforming the Kazakhstani educational system.

As the analysis of works devoted to the problems of the need for the formation of cognitive-communicative competence has shown, this concept traditionally considered in parallel rather than in interconnection.

Cognition and communication are recognized as two main functions of the human language. Initially in the linguistic tradition the priority role was assigned to the communicative function of a language, then in recent decades, marked by the development of the cognitive science, the study of language is viewed as the active process of learning, cognition, mental activity of human consciousness.

According to S.S.Kunanbayeva, one of the priority directions of modernization of education in our country is the idea of competence-based education. The competence-based approach is the basis for achieving a new quality of education. It determines the direction of changes in the educational process. The study of the competence-based approach in education was carried out by such authors as S.S.Kunanbaeva, D.N.Kulibaeva, D.B.Elkonin, I.A.Zimnyaya, A.V.Khutorskoy, E.F. Zeer, J. Raven and others.[1]

The fundamental goal of foreign language education is the formation of the foreign language communicative competence. [2]

Communicative competence is the ability to communicate effectively and efficiently. Communicative competence is a complex formation that includes various structural components. There are many approaches to considering the structure of communicative competence. Communicative competence was first mentioned by Naum Chomsky in 1965, in his writings he draws the line between linguistic and pragmatic competence. Issues related to the definition and essence of the development and formation of the cognitive competence of students were considered in the works of Yu.V. Borisova, A.B. Burovoy, V.I. Ginetsinsky, I.V. Grebenev, B.K. Elmanova, H.B. Kuzmina, C.B. Tretyakova, A.P. Kharina, etc. [3]

Based on the theoretical basis of the development of cognitive-communicative competence of high school students we need to create a model. But first of all there should be particular approaches we will create our model based on. Methodological approaches to

model design are competence-based, communicative, personal-activity, personality-centered, contextual approaches.

The competence - based approach is focused on mastering professional competencies of high school students in the field of pedagogical education. The implementation of the competence approach should provide for the widespread use in the educational process of active and interactive forms of classes (case studies, computer simulations, business and role-playing games, analysis of specific situations, trainings) in combination with extracurricular classes in order to form and develop professional and socio-personal competencies of students.

The communicative approach (A.A. Petrovskaya, A.A. Leontiev, I.A.Kolesnikova) is focused on mastering the communicative experience of mankind by future teachers, productive forms of business and interpersonal communication in professional activities. The implementation of the communicative approach ensures the exchange of linguistic and psychological information between members of the linguistic society to achieve interaction and mutual understanding.

The personal-activity approach involves taking into account individual characteristics in the educational process. The teacher and the student in the context of this approach act as subjects of activity. According to the personality-activity approach, the main means, the decisive condition for the development of personality is the activity in the context of which cognitive-communicative competence is formed. At the same time, subjectivity acts as the students' need for self-organizing, self-controlled, active behavior.

The contextual approach (A.A. Verbitsky, N.V. Borisova) is focused on mastering an integral professional activity in the educational process, where knowledge acts as an oriented basis, a means of its implementation. The implementation of the contextual approach in the process of forming cognitive-communicative competence based on interactive teaching methods is based on for high school students, consistent

modeling in educational activities of the holistic content, forms, conditions of professional activity of future specialists, the implementation of problematic situations based on debates deployed in the educational process.

The model developed on the basis of these approaches is the key for the development of cognitive and communicative competence of high school students. This model can also be used in the development of cognitive - communicative competence of high school students through Internet resources.

Internet resources allow us to successfully develop cognitive-communicative competence through access to a large amount of authentic educational information, computer modeling. Taken as a basis, Internet technologies make it possible to form a qualitatively new efficient learning environment, especially since modernized educational processes involves a whole range of information resources, which is possible only with skillful processing and presentation of information.

Internet resources are song material, which stimulates motivation and promotes better assimilation of language material due to the action of involuntary memorization mechanisms, educational cinema that develops the skills and abilities of perception and understanding of foreign language speech by ear, computer programs, Internet resources which provide individualization of learning and intensification of independent work of students.

The use of Internet resources in foreign language classrooms is one of the modern trends in education, which is currently being actively introduced into Kazakhstani schools.

N. P. Matochkina and A. S. Kinderknecht distinguish four main groups of Internet resources:

- 1) information resources;
- 2) interactive educational resources;
- 3) blogs and forums;
- 4) audio and video podcasts. [4]

Table 1

Internet resources contribute to the formation of basic skills

	Internet resources	Content
1	information resources	theoretical information and materials on the discipline
2	interactive educational resources	network exercises for working in the classroom and at home, in a group and independently; programs with an Internet check of the level of formation of skills;
3	blogs and forums	resources for solving various communicative tasks in real and quasi-real conditions
4	audio and video podcasts	means of using computer technology in the accumulation of visual material

The use of Internet resources contributes to the formation and improvement of basic skills: writing, reading, listening, and speaking.

Table 2

Internet resources contribute to the formation of basic skills

Basic skills	Internet resources
writing	emails, blog articles
reading	slide texts, subtitles, articles in online magazines and blogs
listening	audio tracks, videos, podcasts
speaking	direct communication on Skype and other similar sites, teleconferences

Internet information resources contain, as is known, texts, audio and visual materials on various topics. However, in order for students not to get confused in a large amount of information of various kinds, there was a need to develop special educational Internet resources aimed at meeting educational goals. [5]

Thus, the use of resources of the Internet provides ample opportunities for teaching foreign languages. It can be used by teachers not only for developing skills of listening, reading, writing and speaking, but also for improving communication skills, linguistic and socio-cultural training of students.

In conclusion, the development of the foreign language cognitive-communicative competence can create conditions for the complex use of various cognitive strategies within the framework of solving communicative tasks and for the independent choice of a strategy for solving problem communicative situations in the new conditions of foreign language communication, taking into account the intercultural context, the development of regulatory mechanisms for communication and work with information, and the development of cognitive-communicative competence of high school

students plays an essential role in the modernization of education system of Kazakhstan.

References

1. Kunanbayeva S.S. The modernization of foreign language education: the linguocultural- communicative approach. – United Kingdom Hertfordshire Press, 2013.
2. Modern languages: learning, teaching, assessment: a common European framework of reference. Strasburg, 1996. 260 p.
3. Emelyanova N. S. Development of cognitive-communicative competence of students of colleges as the basis of their educational success: author's ref. dis. ... cand. ped. science. Izhevsk, 2012. 22 p.
4. Matochkina NP, Kinderknecht AS Internet resource for studying a foreign language [Text] / N.P. Matochkina, A.S. Kinderknecht // Philological sciences. Questions of theory and practice. Tambov: Gramota, 2014. № 11 (41). Ch. I. C. 139-141.
5. Klimentyeva B. V. & Klimentyev D. D. (2017). Mass open online courses for students, schoolchildren and teachers. Learned notes. Electronic scientific journal of the Kursk State University, (1 (41)), 165-169.

THE ROLE OF CRITERIA- BASED ASSESSMENT IN THE CONDITION OF UPDATING THE CONTENT OF SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article considers the issue of the transition of Kazakhstan's school education to the updated content. One of the changes in education system of our country is the criteria- based assessment that is used for the assessment of students' achievements. The implemented system of criteria- based assessment is aimed at the development of the student, increasing his/ her motivation to learn. The role of evaluation criteria and regular feedback, understandable for each student and his parents, becomes essential. The effectiveness of the reform of school education will largely depend on the readiness of Kazakhstani teachers to work in the condition of updated system of education, in connection with which the teacher's practice and his research activities become important.

Keywords: criteria- based assessment, formative assessment, summative assessment, student's achievement, school education.

In this modern world, there are a wide range of changes that are taking place in all fields of our life

which made an influence on the globalization of education, the expansion of economic, cultural and other bor-